

INFLUENCE OF DISSOLVED GASSES IN EPOXY RESIN ON RESIN INFUSION PART QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

The standard degassing procedure for VARI processes consists of simply exposing the liquid resin to a lower absolute pressure than atmospheric. However, this methodology is criticized by some researchers. According to M. labordus et al. [1], the standard degassing methodology tends to "de-bubble" the liquid resin rather than degassing it. A series of experiments concerning the characteristics of dissolved gasses in epoxy resin have been performed to determine optimal processing conditions for producing low void content laminates. Studies undertaken included assessing the effectiveness of resin degassing techniques, determining the saturation conditions of dissolved oxygen across a range of pressures, and quantifying the influence of resin dissolved oxygen content on laminate void content and compression strength. Resin degassing pressure was found to be highly influential on the effectiveness of degassing, with pressures under 5mBar recommended to ensure rapid and thorough removal of dissolved gasses. Addition of a nucleation agent to resin was found to increase degassing rates in processes with degassing pressures greater than 15mBar, while the use of deaerating additives in the resin was found to detrimentally impact dissolved oxygen removal. The binary saturation condition of the resin during vacuum assisted resin infusion processes was found to directly impact void content of the cured laminate. Resin that was oversaturated with dissolved gas relative to the set postfill fluid pressure was found to result in average void contents ranging from 1-2% across the laminate, being highest at the resin inlet end. Undersaturated resin resulted in consistently low void contents, being less than 0.2% across the laminate.

1 INTRODUCTION

Henry's Law states that the concentration of a solute gas in a solution is a function of the partial pressure of that gas situated above the solution [2]. From this it can be inferred that decreasing the partial pressure of the gas above a saturated fluid will result in the fluid becoming over saturated. This condition is called supersaturation, and refers to state where a solution contains a higher level of gas than could be dissolved by the solvent at equilibrium under normal circumstances. In this state the system is unstable and gas will diffuse out of the fluid until the new lower saturation gas content is reached and equilibrium is achieved. In vacuum assisted resin infusion processes the gas partial pressure acting on the resin is significantly decreased compared to atmospheric conditions at which the resin is stored. Depending on the resin's initial dissolved gas content, this can cause the resin to become supersaturated. In a supersaturated fluid, gas bubbles will form at nucleation sites, and continue to grow as gas diffuses into them from the fluid. If this occurs during the filling or curing stages of the vacuum assisted resin infusion process then the cured part has a high likelihood of containing voids. In order to develop robust high performance infusion manufacturing processes the characteristics of dissolved gasses in resin have to be determined.

The standard degassing procedure for VARI processes consists of simply exposing the liquid resin to a lower absolute pressure than atmospheric. However, this methodology is criticized by some researchers. According to M. labordus et al. [1], the standard degassing methodology tends to "de-bubble" the liquid resin rather than degassing it. In a liquid resin gas can be present in both dissolved and bubble forms. When the resin is put under vacuum the existing bubbles will expand and rise to the surface, with dissolved gas diffusing into these bubbles. However, if once these initial bubbles are removed there are no suitable nucleation sites, little further degassing will occur as there are few bubbles

into which the dissolved gas can diffuse. In a system that does not contain nucleation sites, the degassing process must follow the homogeneous nucleation mechanism. Wood [3] calculated the critical activation energy of homogeneous nucleation in a composite system as being very large, the corresponding rate of nucleation being subsequently very small. Therefore, degassing resin by simply exposing it to vacuum can in some conditions be very inefficient. As mentioned previously, some materials exhibit favourable bubble nucleation properties. If during the degassing step the resin is put in contact with such material then the significant increase in low energy nucleation sites allows bubble formation to more readily occur. Thus a more efficient degassing of the resin, and not only "de-bubbling", is achieved. Several materials have demonstrated this property including pumice, chalk and sparse unwoven polymers (e.g: Scotch Brite). The type of material used as nucleation agent and the number of nucleation sites influences the degassing efficiency [1,3].

The aim of sparging is to remove the need for the bubble nucleation process through the addition of bubbles into the resin at reduced pressure. In this process a fine filter is placed at the bottom of a container, then the container is filled with liquid resin. As vacuum is applied on the resin, air is allowed to flow into the chamber through a flow limiting valve, passing through the filter resulting in a dispersion of small bubbles that rise through the liquid. Due to the applied vacuum dissolved gasses contained in the resin diffuse into the bubbles [1].

The addition of surfactants to resin also provides another possible avenue for increased degassing efficiency. These molecules are amphiphilic compounds; they are formed by a hydrophobic tail and a hydrophilic head. Their role is to lower the surface tension between two media such as liquid-liquid, solid-liquid or liquid-air interfaces. Due to their dual morphology, surfactants migrate to interfaces and orient themselves to satisfy the attraction of both their head and tail. Surfactants can affect rheological properties of a solution, but also influence surface tension between a liquid and air bubble by either stabilizing their interface, which leads to a stable foam, or inversely by destabilizing the interface. The type of surfactant depends on the chemistry and the size of the head and tail. Thus, possible compositions of surfactants are almost infinite and can be based on a wide range of molecules depending on the desired applications. Surfactants can be used as wetting agents, emulsifiers, foaming or de-foaming agents, dispersants, etc, in foaming, coating and painting industries [4,5]. Some surfactants are used for their deaerating properties. The aim of these agents is to be partially insoluble with epoxy resins, to avoid the formation of a stable solution. When air bubbles are formed, surfactants migrate to the air/liquid interface and prevent the stabilization of bubbles by altering surface tensions. The boundaries of bubbles lose their structural equilibrium and the diffusion of air molecules from the bubble into the resin is encouraged [5,6]. Thus the addition of surfactants to resin during the degassing process has the potential to increase the rate of dissolved gas removal.

Previous work on degassing of resins for use in vacuum infusion has been limited in scope. Labordus et al.[1] investigated the efficiency of standard degassing, degassing with Scotch Brite nucleation agent and degassing via air sparging, with non-degassed resin used as reference. To determine the effectiveness of different out-gassing procedures, Unifilo material was infused at a constant vacuum pressure and the void content of cured laminates was measured to indicate the effectiveness of each method. Non-degassed resin resulted in a high number of voids in manufactured laminates with random and bi-linear void distribution. Standard degassing also resulted in a high number of voids, but no longer in random distribution. No visible voids were created in the laminates infused after degassing the resin with the nucleation material or by air sparging. The efficiency of the air sparging and degassing with Scotch Brite acting as a nucleation agent were also studied by Afendi et al.[7], at a relatively high degassing pressure of 90 mBar. The efficiency of the degassing methods was assessed via measurements taken with a dissolved oxygen meter. In this study sparging was observed to result in the most efficient degassing, with a steady state of 50-60% oxygen removal achieved after 15 minutes. Degassing with a nucleation agent achieved a similar steady state value, but degassing rate was found to be influenced by resin viscosity.

The aim of this study was to develop a thorough understanding of the influences of dissolved gasses on vacuum assisted resin infusion, and provide a foundational methodology which can be applied in order to develop robust high performance infusion manufacturing processes. The efficiency of a range of resin degassing methodologies was assessed across a range of pressures via measurements of dissolved oxygen content. The relationship between resin pressure and dissolved oxygen saturation was

then determined in order to establish the gas saturation state of resin across the pressure range experienced during vacuum infusion. Finally, the influence of resin dissolved oxygen saturation state on laminate mechanical properties and void content was determined.

2 MATERIAL DETAILS AND LAYUP PROPERTIES

Gurit Prime 20 LV, a bisphenol-A-(epichlorhydrin) room temperature curing thermoset epoxy was selected as the resin for this study, paired with Gurit Prime 20 LV Slow Hardener. This system was selected based on intended use in vacuum resin infusion of high performance structures. The ratio of resin to hardener was 100-27 by weight. Resin additives TEGO Glide B 1484 and AIREX 944 were used in this study to investigate the effect of resin additives with deaerating properties on resin degassing. TEGO Glide B 1484 is a polyether siloxane copolymer that acts as a glide and flow additive with deaeration properties. TEGO AIREX 944 consists of silicone tipped deaerating organic polymers and is formulated to act as an effective deaerating agent in a range of resin systems, including epoxies.

For degassing experiments where a nucleation agent was required 20x20x5mm sections of Scotch Brite were used. This was based on its documented property of effectively providing sites for bubble nucleation in resins [1]. The stack layup utilised in this study for vacuum resin infusions consisted of eight layers of Colan MU 4500 D 480g/m² glass fibre unidirectional non-crimp fabric with [+90°/0°/+90°/0°]s fibre orientations. The laminates produced had in-plane dimensions of 350x150mm, with a nominal thickness of 3mm. The SCRIMP methodology was utilized for resin infusion. The setup schematic for each infusion is detailed in Figure 1. All infusions were one dimensional with wetting occurring along the stack length. Infusions were all undertaken at ~22°C and ~50% relative humidity.

Figure 1: Infusion setup schematic

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

3.1 Measurement of Dissolved Gasses

An Atlas Scientific dissolved oxygen probe was used to evaluate the dissolved gas content of resin samples. This is a galvanic type dissolved oxygen probe that provides a reading of the oxygen content in a fluid or gas. It should be noted that this probe is designed for applications in water based environments and its use in epoxy resins is outside its designed use case, thus the stated probe accuracy of $\pm 0.05\text{mg/L}$ should be considered with caution.

Prior to each test series the dissolved oxygen probe was calibrated at two points against fluids with known dissolved content, being air and a deoxygenated fluid. It was noted that probe measurements against these known points could vary significantly after the probe had been exposed to the resin for extended time periods. Subsequently during continuous tests the probe was recalibrated every 24 hours to minimize measurement drift.

3.2 Effectiveness of Degassing Techniques

The effectiveness of three degassing techniques and influence of two resin additives was evaluated. Degassing techniques evaluated in this study include 'standard' degassing, degassing with a nucleation agent, and degassing via sparging. The resin additives evaluated included Tego 1484 and Tego 944, both designed to aid deaeration of resin systems. Degassing effectiveness was evaluated at three vacuum levels for each method: 5mBar, 15mBar, and 50mBar absolute pressure. During preliminary tests it was observed that the selected resin hardener would degrade when directly exposed to atmospheric air for extended periods of time, forming crystalline solids. Subsequently only the bulk epoxy component of resin was studied for this testing regime.

Each experiment consisted of five samples containing 70g of resin. In order to eliminate any geometrical effects, or the influence of scratches within vessels acting as bubble nucleation sites, identical virgin polypropylene containers were used for each test. Prior to the experiment the epoxy resin was stored at room conditions - (23°C, ~60% relative humidity). Sample preparation involved pouring resin into the test vessels two hours prior to the initial dissolved oxygen reading. This time allowed air-bubbles entrained during pouring to rise to the surface of the fluid, reducing their influence on oxygen readings. The initial dissolved oxygen level was measured for each sample to ensure homogeneity in initial conditions between tests. This data was also used to determine saturated dissolved oxygen content at atmospheric conditions.

For standard degassing the resin samples were placed into a vacuum chamber and the pressure decreased to the specified level. For degassing with a nucleation agent a piece of 10×10×3mm Scotch Brite was submerged in each sample prior to degassing. For degassing with resin additives a solution 0.4% by weight of additive was combined with the resin prior to sample pouring for both Tego 944 and Tego 1484. Sample dissolved oxygen levels were measured every 15 minutes until total vacuum exposure time reached one hour. Measurements were then taken after vacuum exposure time reached 2, 3, 24, and 48 hours. In order to take measurements the samples were removed from the vacuum chamber and analysed at atmospheric conditions. Total exposure time to atmospheric conditions was limited to five minutes per measurement point to minimise the influence of oxygen being adsorbed back into the resin.

3.3 Influence of Pressure on Dissolved Oxygen Saturation

The influence of pressure on steady state dissolved gas level in resin was studied to determine the relationship between the saturation level of dissolved oxygen and environmental pressure. Seven experiments were undertaken at varying levels of vacuum pressure, ranging from 5mBar to 600mBar, to determine the saturation point of dissolved oxygen content in resin across the range of pressures resin is exposed to during infusion processes. Each experiment consisted of five samples containing 60g of epoxy without hardener in identical virgin polypropylene containers. At the beginning of each test the specimens initial dissolved oxygen content were measured. The samples were then degassed at the specified pressure via the standard degassing method. Dissolved oxygen measurements were made every 24 hours, with measurements being ceased once the saturation point had been reached and no further decrease in oxygen content was observed. This steady state value was recorded as the saturation point for dissolved oxygen content.

3.4 Influence of Dissolved Oxygen on Laminate Mechanical Properties

Three series of identical fibreglass laminates were infused with resin containing varying levels of dissolved oxygen to determine the influence of dissolved gases in resin on bubble formation, subsequent void content in the vacuum assisted resin infusion process and selected mechanical properties. Panels had the dimensions and setup described in Section 2, and infusion was performed under atmospheric conditions of 22°C and 50% relative humidity. A short release fabric break length of 5-10mm was used at the outlet end of the panel. This provided a path of low resistance for excess resin to be drained from the part after wetout, and allowed laminate fluid pressure to decrease rapidly during the postfill stage of the infusion. Through this mechanism the laminate fluid pressure at cure could be accurately controlled via the vacuum level applied to the outlet of the part during the postfill stage.

Prior to infusion the un-bagged laminate and epoxy resin (excluding hardener) were conditioned in an environmental chamber at 22°C and 50%RH for a period of 48 hours. The layup was then sealed under a flexible chamber and a vacuum of 15mBar absolute pressure was applied to the dry fibre stack for 24 hours. This removed any excess moisture from the laminate in an effort to minimise the influences of humidity. For each infusion 250g of resin and 65g of hardener were degassed at 5mbar for a sample specific time period depending on the desired dissolved oxygen level. After degassing the dissolved oxygen level of the mixed resin was measured. The laminate was then infused at a vacuum of 15mBar absolute pressure. Once total laminate wetout was achieved the resin inlet was closed and a specified postfill pressure was applied at the outlet. Resin curing took place at room conditions for 24 hours. Laminates were then post-cured at 80°C for 10 hours to ensure complete cure of the resin was achieved.

Tests undertaken on the three series of panels included analysis of void content and mechanical testing of laminate compression strength. Five 25 x 25 mm samples were used to estimate the average void content at the inlet and outlet of the panels manufactured through microscopy. The samples were encased in West Systems 105 epoxy and polished on a Buehler Ecomet 300 polishing machine up to P3000 grit. The polished surface of the sample was then photographed in eight sections using a high power microscope, capturing the entire sample width and height. The individual images were then stitched into a single full field image using the software package AutoStitch. ImageJ image processing software was used to manually designate voids through user based boundary selection. These images were then processed via a Matlab script that binarized the images into void and non-void areas. The ratio of void area to total cross sectional area was used to estimate sample void fraction.

Combined loading compression tests were undertaken on the panels in accordance with ASTM D6641 to assess the influence of dissolved oxygen content and deaeration additives on laminate compressive strength. Six samples were tested from the inlet of each panel. Test specimens had a standard width of 13 mm and length of 140 mm, and a nominal thickness of 3 mm.

The first test series involved six laminates that were infused with resin that had been degassed for 0, 1, 5, 10, 20, and 60 minutes respectively. In samples with total degassing times up to ten minutes the epoxy and hardener were mixed prior to degassing. For samples that exceeded ten minutes, epoxy and hardener were degassed separately, then mixed and degassed together for the final 10 minutes. In all tests the total elapsed time from resin mixing to infusion was kept constant at 25 minutes. This prevented differing stages of resin cure progression influencing the infusion process. In all infusions a postfill vacuum pressure of 300 mBar was applied during laminate cure. Testing undertaken on this series included void content analysis at the resin inlet and outlet ends of the panel, and laminate compression strength.

The second test series involved four laminates that were infused with resin that had been degassed to set levels of dissolved oxygen content. Preliminary inspection of the first series of laminates indicated that void content of the cured laminated was a binary function of whether the resin was oversaturated or understated with dissolved gas relative to laminate fluid pressure at cure. To further validate this theory an additional set of panels were manufactured with resin dissolved oxygen contents and corresponding postfill pressures selected such that the resin would be either under saturated or over saturated during postfilling. Two panels were manufactured with low post fill pressures and high post fill pressures in order to ensure the theory was validated across a range of processing conditions. In each case one panel was infused with dissolved gas content and laminate pressure such that the resin was marginally over saturated, while the other was marginally under saturated. In all tests resin and hardener were mixed prior to degassing, and the elapsed time from resin mixing to infusion was kept constant at 25 minutes. Void content analysis was performed at the resin inlet and outlet ends of the cured panel.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Effectiveness Of Degassing Techniques

Degas Method	Pressure	Degas duration (Hours)						
		0.25	0.5	0.75	1	2	24	48
Standard	5mBar	74%	67%	68%	63%	72%	72%	72%
	15mBar	4%	6%	8%	8%	19%	47%	60%
	50mBar	-1%	1%	0%	0%	11%	34%	49%
Scotch Brite	5mBar	77%	76%	74%	72%	66%	76%	71%
	15mBar	9%	13%	17%	20%	33%	58%	66%
	50mBar	5%	6%	2%	7%	15%	47%	63%
Tego 944	5mBar	59%	30%	37%	48%	51%	78%	76%
	15mBar	9%	4%	5%	4%	4%	31%	53%
	50mBar	3%	3%	3%	4%	4%	26%	49%
Tego 1484	5mBar	27%	26%	23%	20%	41%	66%	70%
	15mBar	-4%	0%	-4%	-4%	-4%	36%	56%
	50mBar	-1%	2%	1%	0%	2%	36%	54%

Table 1: Percentage of dissolved oxygen removed by degassing methods at three pressure levels

Plots showing the dissolved oxygen content of resin against time for standard degassing, degassing with Scotch Brite, degassing with Tego 944 and Tego 1484 deaeration additives are presented in Figures 2a and b, c and d respectively. Key results from the investigation on the effectiveness of degassing techniques are summarised in Table 1, which states the average percentage of dissolved oxygen removed from the resin at degas duration. Degassing via the sparging method was removed from the study due to the tendency for sparging to result in micro-bubble formation in the resin. These micro-bubbles were difficult to remove via vacuum due to their small size, and made dissolved oxygen measurements inaccurate.

Low dissolved oxygen removal rates were recorded during the initial high measurement frequency period, with several tests at 5mBar showing increases in dissolved oxygen with increasing degas duration. This can potentially be attributed to the agitating and stirring of the resin required during the measurement process, resulting in air being entrained into the fluid.

For all applied methods, degassing pressure was shown to have a profound impact on degassing rate. When degassing at 5mBar using the standard method the steady state dissolved oxygen level is reached after 15 minutes, compared to 15mBar and 50mBar which have still not reached equilibrium after 48 hours. Large differences in resin dissolved oxygen content were observed between degassing pressures at each measurement duration. After two hours degassing at 5mBar 72% of the initial dissolved oxygen had been removed, while degassing at 15mBar and 50mBar had removed 19% and 11% respectively. Significant differences in dissolved gas content were still present after 48 hours of degassing, with degassing pressures of 5mBar, 15mBar and 50mBar having removed 72%, 60%, and 49% of initial dissolved oxygen.

Degassing with a nucleation agent present, Scotch Brite for these tests, resulted in significantly higher rates of dissolved gas removal at higher degassing pressures, but did not affect degassing rate or steady state value reached at low pressures, when compared to standard degassing. When degassing with Scotch Brite at 5mBar the steady state was again reached after 15 minutes, the dissolved oxygen level being nominally the same as recorded in the standard degassing tests. Degassing at 15mBar and 50mBar again did not reach equilibrium after 48 hours, but lower levels of dissolved oxygen in the resin were reached. Two hours degassing at 15mBar and 50mBar removed 33% and 15% respectively of the initial dissolved oxygen, 14% and 4% higher than achieved via standard degassing. 48 hours of degassing at 15mBar and 50mBar resulted in the removal of 66% and 60% of the initial dissolved oxygen, 6% and 14% higher than achieved via standard degassing respectively.

Degassing with deaeration additives present in the resin resulted in significantly lower rates of dissolved gas removal across all degassing pressures. Dissolved oxygen measurements were also observed to vary significantly between samples when degassing at 5mBar, resulting in large standard deviations in the measured values. For Tego 944, degassing at 5mBar did result in steady state dissolved

oxygen level being reached, but only after 24 hours. Two hours degassing at 5mBar, 15mBar and 50mBar removed 51%, 4% and 4% respectively of the initial dissolved oxygen, being 21%, 15% and 7% lower than achieved via standard degassing. After 48 hours of degassing dissolved oxygen levels were comparable to standard degassing across all pressures, once the large standard deviations of the samples degassed with Tego 944 were taken into account.

For Tego 1484, degassing performance was comparable to that of Tego 944. Two hours degassing at 5mBar removed 41% of the initial dissolved oxygen, while degassing at 15mBar and 50mBar was observed to result in negligible removal of dissolved gas. This resulted in performance 31%, 19% and 11% lower than achieved via standard degassing. 48 hours of degassing at 5mBar, 15mBar and 50mBar resulted in the removal of 70%, 56% and 54% of the initial dissolved oxygen, being comparable to the levels achieved via standard degassing.

Figure 2: Resin dissolved oxygen content with time for standard degassing (a), degassing with a nucleation agent (b), degassing with deaeration additive Tego 944 (c) and Tego 1484 (d).

4.2 Influence of Pressure on Dissolved Oxygen Saturation

Figure 3 shows the measured values of dissolved oxygen content across the range of resin fluid pressures measured, with the average initial dissolved oxygen content of samples prior to degassing in the resin degassing method effectiveness experiments being used as a data point for saturation at atmospheric pressure. A strong linear correlation is observed, described in Equation 1, where DO_2 and P represent saturated dissolved oxygen content in mg/L and absolute fluid pressure in mBar respectively. From this relationship the saturation condition of the resin studied here can be determined based on measured dissolved oxygen and applied pressure. Resin with measured dissolved oxygen content greater

than and less than the calculated saturation value for a given resin fluid pressure are oversaturated and undersaturated respectively. These regions have been presented in Figure 3. The linear nature of the relationship between dissolved oxygen content and applied pressure is in agreement with Henry’s law which states that at a constant temperature, the amount of a given gas dissolved in a given type and volume of liquid is directly proportional to the partial pressure of that gas in equilibrium with that liquid. This is described in Equation 2, where p , k_H and c represent partial pressure of the solute above the fluid, Henry’s law constant (which is dependent on the solute being considered), and solute concentration in solution. However, the non-zero intercept of the measured relationship is in disagreement with Henry’s law, which implies that solubility tends to zero as pressure approaches absolute vacuum. This suggests a constant offset error is present in readings taken by the dissolved oxygen probe used in the tests undertaken, likely caused by issues with calibration or the fact that the probe is not rated for use in epoxy resins. Subsequently, all measurements of dissolved oxygen presented in this paper should be taken as comparative rather than absolute values.

Figure 3: Plot of saturated dissolved oxygen content against resin fluid pressure, with oversaturated and undersaturated regions labelled

$$DO_2 = 0.005.P + 1.94 \tag{1}$$

$$p = k_H.c \tag{2}$$

4.3 Influence of Dissolved Oxygen on Laminate Mechanical Properties

Total Degassing Time	0 min	1 min	5 min	10 min	20 min	60 min
Dissolved Oxygen	7.3	5.8	3.5	2.8	1.9	1.5
Postfill Pressure	300	300	300	300	300	300
Resin Saturation	Over	Over	Under	Under	Under	Under
Void Content – Inlet	2.1	2.7	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
Void Content – Outlet	<0.1	1.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
CLC Strength	313	337	291	328	337	341

Table 2: Summary of results from infusion series 1

Key results from the first experimental series on the influence of dissolved oxygen on laminate mechanical properties are summarised in Table 2. The dissolved oxygen content of the resin infused into the specimens ranged from 7.3mg/L for resin that underwent no degassing, to 1.5mg/L for resin that was degassed for 60 minutes. These results are largely in agreement with the values obtained during the previous tests for resin degassing method effectiveness. The lower value of dissolved oxygen reached in the 60 minute degas duration sample (1.5mg/L) compared to the steady state saturation value

reached in tests for resin degassing effectiveness and influence of pressure on dissolved oxygen saturation (~2.0mg/L) can be attributed to the addition of hardener which has the effect of both lowering the fluids viscosity and changing its chemical composition. Resin with high dissolved oxygen content was observed to have a significantly shorter pot life when compared with resin that had been thoroughly degassed.

Void content of the cured panels was found to vary significantly at the inlet end, and directly correlate to the saturation condition of the resin. Saturation condition of the resin was determined from the measured relationship of steady state dissolved oxygen content relative to resin pressure, shown in Figure 3. Samples with dissolved oxygen contents higher than the saturation value at the set postfill resin pressure were deemed oversaturated, while those with lower dissolved oxygen contents were deemed undersaturated.

Samples with oversaturated resin were found to have high void contents (>2%) at the inlet in all cases. An example of the void distribution in these samples is shown in the microscopy image presented in Figure 4a. It should be noted that that the elongated dark regions in the tows running parallel to the cross section are the result of fibres breaking during the polishing processes, not voids. Here it can be seen that voids are largely formed in the inter-tow regions, and are of a significant size. Void content at the outlet end of oversaturated samples was observed to be significantly lower. Figure 4b typifies the void distribution found at the outlet of oversaturated samples, with significant size voids forming in the inter-tow regions at a much lower concentration than the inlet. The void content gradient along the infusion direction can be speculated to be a result of the fibres acting as bubble nucleation sites. Previous studies have found that glass fibres can act as effective bubble nucleation sites in oversaturated resins [1]. Subsequently, as oversaturated resin is draw into the laminate bubbles will begin to form and gas will continually diffuse into them. Thus it can be hypothesised that as the resin flows along the laminate length a dissolved gas gradient will form, the outlet end having a lower concentration than the inlet, resulting in the observed difference in void content.

Samples with undersaturated resin were found to have negligible void contents (<0.1%) at both the inlet and outlet ends. An example of the void distribution in these samples is shown in Figure 4c. It can be seen that there is no substantial void formation in either intra-tow or inter-tow regions. The consistent low void content can be explained by the ability of undersaturated resin to absorb entrapped air back into solution. Although bubbles will not form in undersaturated resin due to dissolved gasses nucleating and coming out of solution, air can still be entrapped as a result of differences in inter-tow and intra-tow resin flow rates. When this occurs in oversaturated resin, dissolved gas will diffused into the entrapped bubble causing it to expand, increasing laminate void content. By contrast, in undersaturated resins this entrapped air dissolves into the surrounding resin, until resin reaches local saturation or the bubble is depleted.

Figure 4: a) Inlet laminate cross section from oversaturated sample, b) Outlet laminate cross section from overstaturated sample, c) Inlet laminate cross section from undersaturated sample.

The results of the combined loading compression strength tests with one standard deviation error bars are presented in Table 2. Statistical analysis was undertaken on the test results to determine the statistical significance of any differences. ANOVA analysis of the results indicated that there was no statistically significant difference between the panels with varying dissolved oxygen content, returning a P-value of 0.78. This result shows that although increasing dissolved oxygen content leads in an increase in void formation within the laminate, the mechanical strength of the resin is not substantially impacted. Due to the compression test specimens being cut from the centre of the test panels and the

graded void content along the infusion direction of the laminate, it is anticipated that the compression testing results have not been affected as significantly as could be expected if the samples were cut from the panel inlets. Laminate compression strength at the inlet is theorised to be more substantially impacted due to the significant increase in local void content present in oversaturated samples.

Resin Saturation	Undersaturated						Oversaturated			
Test Series	1	1	1	1	3	3	1	1	3	3
Dissolved O₂ (mg/L)	1.5	1.9	2.8	3.4	2.4	4.1	5.8	7.3	4.4	5.1
Postfill Pressure (mBar)	300	300	300	300	150	500	300	300	100	450
O₂ Saturation (mg/L)	3.4	3.4	3.4	3.4	2.7	4.4	3.4	3.4	2.4	4.1
Resin Saturation %	44%	55%	82%	100%	89%	93%	171%	215%	183%	124%
Void Content - Inlet %	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.2	0.2	2.7	2.1	2.9	3.1
- Outlet %	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.1	0.1	1.1	<0.1	1.2	0.4
- Average %	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	1.9	1.1	2.1	1.8

Table 3: Summary of results from infusion series 1 and 2

Combined key results from the first and second experimental series concerning the influence of dissolved oxygen on laminate void content are summarised in Table 3. This combined data series was used to test the hypothesis, based on preliminary inspection of the first series of laminates, that void content of a cured laminated is a binary function of whether the resin was oversaturated or understated with dissolved gas relative to laminate fluid pressure at cure, across a wide range of infusion conditions. Here the O₂ saturation value is derived from the measured relationship between steady state resin dissolved oxygen content and resin fluid pressure, presented in Equation 1, taking the set infusion postfill pressure as the input. The resin saturation was calculated taking the measured infused resin dissolved oxygen content as a percentage of the derived oxygen saturation.

Figure 5a shows the relationship between resin saturation and average laminate void content. It is apparent that void content appears to be a binary function of the oversaturation condition, confirming the proposed hypothesis. If infused resin is oversaturated relative to the set postfill fluid pressure, average void content across the panel ranges from 1-2%. If the infused resin is undersaturated relative to the set postfill fluid pressure, the void content decreases significantly, ranging from 0.1-0.2%. There is no correlation between percentage saturation and void content. Higher levels of oversaturation do not result in greater void formation, nor do lower levels of undersaturation decrease void content.

Figure 5: a) Plot of average laminate void content against resin oxygen saturation, b) Plot of void content of laminates at measured resin dissolved oxygen contents and set postfill pressures.

Figure 5b provides an effective overall summary of the results of multiple investigations, combining the measured relationship between resin fluid pressure and dissolved oxygen saturation with the measured average void content of the samples produced in series one and three. Data point area correlates to void content, and the oversaturated and understaturated regions on the graph relate to the condition of the resin at any given pressure and dissolved oxygen content. From Figure 5b it is clear across a range of conditions that ensuring resin is undersaturated with dissolved gasses is key to ensuring a low level of porosity in vacuum assisted resin infused laminates. This highlights the importance of active measurement of both laminate fluid pressure and resin dissolved oxygen content in high performance infusion manufacturing processes.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A series of experiments concerning the characteristics of dissolved gasses in epoxy resin have been performed to determine optimal processing conditions for producing low void content laminates. Studies undertaken included assessing the effectiveness of resin degassing techniques, determining the saturation conditions of dissolved oxygen across a range of pressures, measuring the absorption rate of oxygen into degassed epoxy, and quantifying the influence of resin dissolved oxygen content on laminate void content and compression strength.

Resin degassing pressure was found to be highly influential on the effectiveness of degassing, with pressures under 5mBar recommended to ensure rapid and thorough removal of dissolved gasses. Addition of a nucleation agent to resin was found to increase degassing rates in processes with degassing pressures greater than 15mBar, while the use of deaerating additives in the resin was found to detrimentally impact dissolved oxygen removal.

The saturation point of dissolved oxygen in resin was found to linearly correlate with resin pressure, enabling a binary saturation condition to be easily determined based on measurements of dissolved oxygen content and pressure.

The binary saturation condition of the resin during vacuum assisted resin infusion processes was found to directly impact void content of the cured laminate. Resin that was oversaturated with dissolved gas relative to the set postfill fluid pressure was found to result in average void contents ranging from 1-2% across the laminate, being highest at the resin inlet end. Undersaturated resin resulted in consistently low void contents, being less than 0.2% across the laminate.

This work represents the first comprehensive investigation on the effects of dissolved oxygen content on void formation in resin infusion processes, covering a wide range of key characteristics required to design and develop robust manufacturing processes. It shows that resin dissolved oxygen content is a key manufacturing parameter that requires active measurement to ensure low void content in high performance infusion manufacturing processes, and highlights the need for resin specific dissolved gas measurement equipment to be developed.

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